

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF WATER DESALINATION IN HUMIDIFICATION–DEHUMIDIFICATION UNIT USING POTTERY TUBES

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Abstract:

The objectives of this study, in generally, to produce pottery tubes manufactured from local materials, Manufacturing device for the water desalination and the production of water. The use of river water of the dijl, kraat-Baghdadin water production. In this study presented the performance of Water Desalination Humidification-Dehumidification Systems by the use of a different number of tubes, arranged, different water flow rate and different air velocity to obtain a higher amount of water produced. Experimental results show that the amount of water produced in dehumidification unit is 30 ml/2 hours for five pottery staggered tubes arrangement by two rows, 20 ml/2 hours for six pottery inline tubes arrangement by two rows, 55 ml/2 hours for seven pottery staggered tubes arrangement by three rows, 55 ml/2 hours for eight pottery staggered tubes arrangement by three rows and 60 ml/2 hours for ten hollow ceramic pipes staggered tubes arrangement by four rows at 100 ml/min water flow rate and 199 l/s air flow rate. The percentage increase in water production are 166.6%, 230%, 163.6%, 169%, and 165% for five pottery tubes, six pottery tubes, seven pottery tubes, eight pottery tubes and ten pottery tubes at 500 ml/min water flow rate and 199 l/s air flow rate. Finally, increasing the number of tubes increases production. Arrangement of pottery tubes by method staggered tubes the best from inline tubes.

Key Words: Humidification, Dehumidification, Pottery, Production & Desalination

1. Introduction:

Desalination can be defined as any process that removes salts from water. Desalination processes may be used in municipal, industrial, or commercial applications. With improvements in technology, desalination processes are becoming cost-competitive with other methods of producing usable water for our growing needs. The world's water consumption rate is doubling every 20 years, outpacing by two times the rate of population growth. The availability of good quality water is on the decline and water demand is on the rise. Worldwide availability of fresh water for industrial needs and human consumption is limited. Various industrial and developmental activities in recent times have resulted in increasing the pollution level and deteriorating the water quality. There are several desalination technologies and several ways to classify them. The desalination techniques can be divided into two main categories; the first categories are Membrane Desalination Technologies. Membrane desalination uses membranes to separate fresh water from saline feed-water. Feed-water is brought to the surface of a membrane, which selectively passes water and excludes salts. Sometimes called single phase (membrane processes) In the single phase processes membranes are used in three commercially important desalination processes, Reverse Osmosis (RO) distillation [Strathmann (2004), Wong (2012)], Electro Dialysis (ED) distillation and Nano filtration distillation [Yunhui (2017)]. The second categories are Thermal Desalination Technologies. Thermal desalination involves distillation processes where saline feed-water is heated to vaporize, causing fresh water to evaporate and leave behind a highly saline solution, namely the brine. Freshwater is then obtained from vapor cooling and condensation. Sometimes called phase change (thermal processes). In the phase change process, a thermal energy source, such as fossil fuels, nuclear energy or solar energy may be used to evaporate water, which is condensed to provide fresh water. The phase change desalination processes described here include, solar distiller, Multi-Stage Flash (MSF) distillation [Raj (2016)], Multi-Effect distillation (MED), Thermal Vapor Compression (TVC) distillation, [Sharon (2015)] Humidification-Dehumidification (HD) and Freezing distillation. Many researches were accomplished in this field. Younis (1993) have used a spray tower as the humidifier in their HD systems. They have tested the spray tower humidifier by varying the ratio of water-to-dry air mass flow rate and keeping both the inlet water temperature and absolute humidity constant while the inlet air temperature (80°C) was higher than that of the water sprayed temperature (60°C). They found that increasing the amount of water sprayed has increased the absolute outlet humidity. However, further increase in the water quantity resulted in air cooling and this condensed some of the water vapor content in the air. This means a decrease in the absolute humidity, although the outlet air is always saturated. Therefore, for air heated HDH cycles, there is an optimum value of the mass flow ratio which gives maximum air humidity. This fact promotes the use of multi-stage air heater and humidifier combinations to increase the fresh water production. Yamali and Solmusf 2008 have studied the pad

humidifier unit which consists of four pads in series, made of plastic material and it forms the wetted surface of the humidifier. The size of each pad is 35 × 35 × 12 cm. They were mounted vertically in a metal box of 35 cm wide, 60 cm long and 45 cm height. This metal box made of galvanized steel of 2 mm thickness, was constructed by welding and it was thermally insulated. At the top of the box, there is a liquid sprayer, which sprays liquid water to each pad cartridge, while at the bottom there is a water storage tank, where the water is collected as it drains down the pad cartridge. Thus, the water flows downward, while the air passes in a cross flow direction through the openings of the pad Cartridge. The air is humidified as it comes in contact with the wetted surface of the pad. Amer et al. (2009) have designed a humidifier of 200 cm height, 80 cm length, and 50 cm width. A packing material is fixed inside the humidifier to have a surface area of approximately 6 m². The packing is supported such that it does not block the air flow and remains continuously wet. The water has been sprayed on the packing material using a hydraulic grid. A movable door has been provided to facilitate the changing of packing material easily to achieve a max of productivity of 5.8 l/hr. Hermosillo et al. (2011) have studied water desalination by air humidification. In the experimental study, the condenser portion is a box of 0.305 × 0.305 m of cross section and 0.335 m of length. The heat exchanger inside this box is a liquid-gas type, with water flowing up wards through 105 vertical tubes and air flowing through 57 horizontal fins. The total heat exchange area, is 3.5 m². The evaporator portion is a box of the same cross section and 0.40 m of length.

2. Description of the Experimental Apparatus:

In the air humidification and dehumidification unit of this work, the air acts as a carrier fluid. Without boiling the water evaporation occurs. The air is moistened in humidification unit of the system part and moved to a cooler part where water vapor condenses to release the enthalpy from the condensation. In the dehumidifier, this heat can be recovered and used to heat the water. Air flow in a closed loop of humidifier (evaporator) to dehumidifier (condenser) and vice versa. The flow of water in an open circle is as follows: The river water enters the system into a coiled tube as the coolant flows through the condenser, thus cooling the wet air and picking up its change from the enthalpy. It leaves the condenser at the water temperature outlet after gaining heat from the wet air. The hot water enters to evaporation unit. The water leaves the system. The experimental apparatus, after modulation, consists generally of the evaporative cooling (humidification unit), dehumidifiers unit (Condensers), water circuit and the air circuit. A schematic diagram of the experimental apparatus is shown in Figure 1.

Full details of the portions of the apparatus, measuring instruments and data analysis are presented in following sections.

1. Supply Tank	8. Potterytubes	15. Temp. Control
2. Controlling Valve	9. Reciver Tank	16. Air Speed Variable
3. Water Pump	10. Local Speed Measurement	17. In-Off Water Pump
4. Water Temp. Sensor	11. Localair Temp. Measurement	18. Ambient Temp.
5. Iinsulator	12. Collector Tank 1	19. By-Pass Valve
6. Coil Copper Heat Exchanger	13. Air Fan	20. Collector Tank 2
7. Water Flow Meter	14. Heater	21. Make-Up Water Tank

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the experimental apparatus

2.1 Water Desalination Humidification-Dehumidification (HD) Dimension:

Water desalination Humidification Dehumidification (HD) unit consists from iron frame; it consists of ten parts, each part of 5 mm thickness, connected together by screws and nuts. Five parts is rectangular box of external dimensions (250 mm×250 mm×500 mm height), one part is rectangular box of external dimensions

(250 mm×250 mm×1000 mm height), and four parts as shown in this fig (2). The face of the water desalination Humidification-Dehumidification (HD) unit made of material is transparent Plexiglas glass sheet at 4 mm thickness to provide clear view of the actions occurring inside the unit.

Figure 2: Water desalination Humidification-Dehumidification (HD) dimension

2.1.1 Humidification Unit (Test Section):

Humidification Unit consists from pottery porous tubes. Pottery porous tubes manufactured from local materials, the red clay soil is well known and commonly used in the pottery artist’s work. It needs a higher firing degree to mature, which is available as the purest red clay soil at Kraat- Baghdad. The red clay produced pottery porous tubes, the set is of 30 mm in out diameter with 4 mm a thickness and 250 mm length. Humidification unit used ten pottery tubes. Pottery porous tube consists of the two cover, two join, two Plastic tapes (3.6 mm thickness) and two silicone heater hose (SAE J20 R3 cl a 1.0 in (25.40mm)).

It was arranged pipes presented in Humidification unit shown in following part. figure (3) show that schematic tubes arrangement in Humidification unit of width 250 mm, depth 250mm and height 500 mm with different number of pottery tubes of out radius 15 mm, thickness 4 mm, Transfer tube pitch (Horizontal pitch) XT 65mm, and Longitudinal tube pitch (Vertical pitch) XL 65 mm.

Figure 3: Schematic tubes arrangement

The use of a different number of tubes and arranged as follows:

- ✓ The use ten pottery tubes in four rows with staggered tubes arrangement.
- ✓ The use eight pottery tubes in three rows with staggered tubes arrangement.
- ✓ The use seven pottery tubes in three rows with staggered tubes arrangement.
- ✓ The use six pottery tubes in two rows with inline tubes arrangement.
- ✓ The use five pottery tubes in two rows with staggered tubes arrangement.

2.1.2 Dehumidification Unit:

Dehumidification unit contains on Helical Coil heat exchanger as show in this figure (4). Helical Coil heat exchanger was designed and manufactured for the present work. A copper tube of 15.25 m length (L) and 15.875 mm internal diameter is turned into 28 turns of 170 mm coil diameter, and 35 mm pitch. Shell part is rectangular box of external dimensions (250 mm×250 mm×1000 mm height). Shell part is rectangular box of external dimensions (250 mm×250 mm×1000 mm height). The face of the dehumidification unit is made of transparent Plexiglas glass sheet to indicate the condensation process. Supply water enters the system into coiled tube as a cooling fluid at inlet water (point 1) and flows through the condenser to cool the humid air and condense water vapor. It leaves the condenser at outlet water (point 2). The humid air enters hot and wet at point (3). The air will be cooled at point (4) is comprised of sensible heat and latent heat. The sensible cooling presented as air temperature decrease by absorbing heat by supply water.

Figure 4: Helical Coil Heat Exchanger

3. Instrumentations:

Air speed is measured by hot wire anemometer model YK-2005AH of range of 0.2 – 20 m/s with 1% error. Water volumetric flow meter of (100 to 500 ml/min) range was used with error of reading about of 1 %. A water pump of (370 W) with a maximum volumetric flow rate (30 l/min) and a maximum head (30 m). An air fan of (62 W) with a maximum 2700 r.p.m. The system is connected by the PP-R (Poly Propylene –Random) pipe. The specifications PP-R pipes are maximum pressure (0.1 Bar), maximum temperature (95 °C), 17 mm internal diameter and 25.4 mm outer diameter.

4. Experimental Results:

The results of calculations for water production with different water flow rate, different air flow rate and different number of tubes and arranged. Figure (5) shows the change of water production in dehumidification unit versus water flow rate for different number of tubes and arranged. Figure show that increases water production with water flow rate increases. It can be shown the amount of water produced at water flow rate of 100 ml / min and 135 l / s air flow rate as follows:

- ✓ 57 ml for 2 hours with ten pottery tubes staggered tubes arrangement by four rows.
- ✓ 52 ml for 2 hours with eight pottery tubes staggered tubes arrangement by three rows.
- ✓ 52 ml for 2 hours with seven pottery tubes staggered tubes arrangement by three rows.
- ✓ 19 ml for 2 hours with six pottery tubes inline tubes arrangement by two rows.
- ✓ 29 ml for 2 hours with for five pottery tubes staggered tubes arrangement by two rows.

Table 1 show that increase percentage in the water production at 200, 300, 400 and 500 ml/min water flow rate respectively and 135 l/s air flow rate with different number of tubes and arranged.

Table 1: Percentage water production increase at 135 l/s air flow rate in dehumidification unit

Number of tubes	Water Flow Rate			
	200 ml/min	300 ml/min	400 ml/min	500 ml/min
Ten pottery tubes staggered tubes arrangement by four rows	77.19%	124.5%	145.6%	171.9%
Eight pottery tubes staggered tubes arrangement by three rows	48%	121.1%	136.5%	173%
Seven pottery tubes staggered tubes arrangement by three rows	48%	121.1%	134.6%	169.2%

Six pottery tubes inline tubes arrangement by two rows	52.6%	157.8%,	189.4%,	236.8%
Five pottery tubes staggered tubes arrangement by two rows	31%	82.7%	120.6%	168.9%

Figure 6 shows the change of water production in dehumidification unit versus water flow rate for different number of tubes and arranged. Figure show that increases water production with water flow rate increases. It can be shown the amount of water produced at water flow rate of 100 ml / min and 170 l / s air flow rate as follows:

- ✓ 59 ml for 2 hours with ten pottery tubes staggered tubes arrangement by four rows.
- ✓ 53 ml for 2 hours with eight pottery tubes staggered tubes arrangement by three rows.
- ✓ 53 ml for 2 hours with seven pottery tubes staggered tubes arrangement by three rows.
- ✓ 20 ml for 2 hours with six pottery tubes inline tubes arrangement by two rows.
- ✓ 30 ml for 2 hours with for five pottery tubes staggered tubes arrangement by two rows.

Table 2 show the percentage increase in the water production at 200 , 300 , 400 and 500 ml/min water flow rate respectively and 170 l/s air flow rate with different number of tubes and arranged.

Table 2: Percentage water production increase at 170 l/s air flow rate in dehumidification unit

Number of tubes	Water Flow Rate			
	200 ml/min	300 ml/min	400 ml/min	500 ml/min
Ten pottery tubes staggered tubes arrangement by four rows	74.5%	120.3%,	140.6%	166.1%
Eight pottery tubes staggered tubes arrangement by three rows	49%	122.6%	139.6%	173.5%
Seven pottery tubes staggered tubes arrangement by three rows	49%	122.6%	137.7%	173.5%
Six pottery tubes inline tubes arrangement by two rows	50%	150%	180%	220%
Five pottery tubes staggered tubes arrangement by two rows	33.3%	80%	120%	163.3%

Figure 7 shows the change of water production in dehumidification unit versus water flow rate for different number of tubes and arranged. Figure show that increases water production with water flow rate increases. It can be shown the amount of water produced at water flow rate of 100 ml / min and 199 l / s air flow rate as follows:

- ✓ 60 ml for 2 hours with ten pottery tubes staggered tubes arrangement by four rows.
- ✓ 55 ml for 2 hours with eight pottery tubes staggered tubes arrangement by three rows.
- ✓ 55 ml for 2 hours with seven pottery tubes staggered tubes arrangement by three rows.
- ✓ 20 ml for 2 hours with six pottery tubes inline tubes arrangement by two rows.
- ✓ 30 ml for 2 hours with for five pottery tubes staggered tubes arrangement by two rows.

Table 3 show the percentage increase in the water production at 200, 300, 400 and 500 ml/min water flow rate respectively and 199 l/s air flow rate with different number of tubes and arranged. The condenser chamber, where the evaporated water is collected after 25 to 30 min. Figures (5 to 7) show that the increased air flow rate led to small increase in water production. Increasing the number of tubes increases production. Arrangement pottery tubes by method staggered tubes the best from inline tubes. Where we note that the water production used five pottery tubes staggered tubes arrangement by two rows the best from used six pottery tubes inline tubes arrangement by two rows.

Table 3: Percentage water production increase at 199 l/s air flow rate in dehumidification unit

Number of tubes	Water flow rate			
	200 ml/min	300 ml/min	400 ml/min	500 ml/min
Ten pottery tubes staggered tubes arrangement by four rows	75%	125%	141.1%	165%
Eight pottery tubes staggered tubes arrangement by three rows	45.4%	118.1%	136.3%,	169%
Seven pottery tubes staggered tubes arrangement by three rows	45.4%	116.3%	132.7%	163.3%
Six pottery tubes inline tubes arrangement by two rows	55%	150%	185%	230%
Five pottery tubes staggered tubes arrangement by two rows	33.3%	83.3%	123.3%	166.7%

Figure 5: Variation of water production in Dehumidification unit with different number of tubes and arranged of pottery tubes at 135 l/s air flow rate

Figure 6: Variation of water production in Dehumidification unit with different number of tubes and arranged of pottery tubes 170 l/s air flow rate

Figure 7: Variation of water production in Dehumidification unit with different number of tubes and arranged of pottery tubes at 199 l/s air flow rate

6. Conclusion:

In this paper the performances of water desalination humidification-dehumidification systems by used pottery tubes was investigated experimentally. Based on the investigation results, the following conclusions are drawn:

- ✓ The increased air flow rate led to small increase in water production.
- ✓ The increases water production with water flow rate increases.

- ✓ Increasing the number of tubes increases production.
- ✓ The water production used five pottery staggered tubes arrangement by two rows the best from used sex pottery inline tubes arrangement by two rows.

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